

SATIRE AND SOCIAL CRITICISM IN “NEW PIKIN 1&2” AND “NAIJA NINJA”

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Abstract

There is indeed a paucity of formalist criticism on contemporary Nigerian television dramas. Quite often, Nigerian television drama scholars, critics, and aficionados tend to focus so much attention on the exegesis of the contents of Nigerian television dramas without caring much about the aspect of the techniques through which meanings can be unlocked. Granted, as some have argued, that content is very central in art criticism, but equally important is the aspect of technique, for, in essence, the technique remains the sole vehicle for conveying meaning to the audience; as well as for giving the work its aesthetic balance. There is, therefore, the urgent need to turn attention to the aspect of form in the discussion of the content of artistic works. This study examines how Amaka Igwe deployed satire for social criticism in “New Pikin 1&2” and “Naija Ninja”- two Nigerian television drama episodes from her award-winning family television drama entitled Fuji House of Commotion. The study is qualitative and exegetical and is anchored on a combination of formalist and sociological critical theories. It concludes that in the television dramas being studied, Amaka Igwe dexterously deployed satire to effectively ridicule the high and irrational craving for fake foreign cultures among many contemporary Nigerian youths which, unfortunately, makes most of them denigrate and lose their rich African cultural and moral values.

Keywords: satire, social criticism, Nigerian television drama, Fuji House of Commotion.

I. Introduction

The late Uzoamaka Audrey, popularly known as Amaka Igwe, was a prolific and accomplished Nigerian television scriptwriter, producer, director, teacher, entrepreneur, filmmaker, and broadcasting executive whose artistic dexterity, ingenuity, and versatility earned her multiple awards. Born to Isaac and Patience Ene on the 2nd of January, 1963, in Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria, the multi-talented Amaka Igwe began to exhibit her great theatrical skills quite early during her primary and secondary school education, especially at the Awkunanaw High School, Enugu, Enugu State, and later at Idia College, Benin, Edo State, where she obtained an A level certificate. In both institutions, she amazingly distinguished herself variously as a boxer, footballer, and admirable dancer of the famous 'Atilogwu' Igbo cultural dance.

Although she later studied Education and Religious Studies at the University of Ife (now Obafemi Awolowo University) Ile Ife, Osun State, Nigeria, and thereafter Library and Information Science (for Master's degree) at the University of Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria, she, nevertheless, remained highly devoted to her artistic calling. Amaka Igwe first courted national fame as the writer and producer of the popular television soaps: *Checkmate*, *Solitaire*, *Now We Are Married*, *Infinity Hospital*, *Bless this House*, and *Fuji House of Commotion* so that by the time she later came into film production, she had already become a household name in the international theatre scene. Her popular films include: *Rattle Snake 1, 2 & 3*, *Violated 1 & 2*, *To Live Again*, *Full Circle*, and *Barber's Wisdom*. Both her television dramas and films were designed to entertain and x-ray-cum-correct some of the common socio-political anomalies in contemporary Nigeria. Her various works have attracted some critical attention, though not mainly from the aspect of her craft from which the present studies are being carried out.

This study is an attempt to demonstrate how Amaka Igwe skilfully deployed the technique of satire for social criticism in "New Pikin 1 & 2" and "Naija Ninja", both taken from her block-buster family television drama program- *Fuji House of Commotion*. This has become urgent and significant because at present no scholar, to the best of our knowledge, has extensively discussed this crucial topic in Amaka Igwe's scholarship. The study will be done in four phases, with the first focusing on the elucidation of the key concepts: "satire" and "social criticism"; the second on illuminating the tenets of formalist and sociological theories which form the theoretical framework for this study; the third on the synopses of "New Pikin 1 & 2" and "Naija Ninja"; and the fourth on Amaka Igwe's deployment of satire for social criticism in the television dramas and its lessons to contemporary Nigerian youths who are being blown and buffeted by the winds of Western colonial mentality.

Satire is a common literary term whose definition and discussion have engaged the attention of many literary scholars and critics over time. According to Northrop Frye, Sheridan Baker, and George Perkins, the term "satire" evolved from the Latin root "satura" which "denotes a mixed dish, or metaphorically, a medley, a derivation from satyra" (413). They further explain that satire "arose as a specific verse form in Latin Literature practiced by Horace, Juvenal, and Persius" (413). Implicit in their view above is that satire evolved primarily as a form of literature rather than as a literary technique. However, it is noteworthy that satire later developed as a literary technique with which writers and theatre producers adeptly ridicule societal vices and their perpetrators. In this regard, M.H. Abrams and Geoffrey Harpham define satire as "the literary art of diminishing or derogating a subject by making it ridiculous and evoking towards it attitudes of amusement, contempt, scorn or indignation" (186). Similarly, Holman and Harmon define satire as "a literary manner that blends a critical attitude with HUMOR and WIT to improve human institutions" (original emphasis 447).

As Holman and Harmon's definition suggests, the satirist ingeniously manipulates humor laced with irony for social criticism. In his inaugural lecture entitled: *Ridentem Dicere Verum: Literature and the Common Welfare* (1988), Charles Nnolim has noted that to the satirist, humor constitutes the proverbial honey that drives the bitter pill of criticism down the throat of humans. He goes on to quote Horace, the great Roman satirist, as saying that good satirists "often speak the truth laughing" ("ridentem dicere verum") (26). Furthermore, it is worth noting that satirists often present characters that symbolise their objects of attack as arrogant but ironically ignorant people *ala alazons* who are eventually outwitted by their unassuming counterparts, the eirons. Thus, in the end, the gifted satirist successfully deflates the pompous alazon thereby laying bare the arrant stupidity and emptiness embodied in the braggadocio.

In effect, then, satire is a deflationary technique through which satirists launch series of powerful attacks on their objects of ridicule so that the audience can learn from their frailties. Matthew Hogard rightly submits that "satire has its origin in a state of mind which is critical and aggressive, usually one of irritation at the least example of human absurdity, inefficiency or wickedness" (10). M.H. Abrams and Geoffrey Harpham concur that "satire has usually been justified by those who practice it as a corrective of human folly" (353). And Oyeh Otu strongly proclaims that "Satire is one of the strongest literary weapons a writer can use not only to ridicule and criticize society but most importantly to also prick the conscience of society and awaken moral rejuvenation in man's quest for social transformation" (207). Chidi Ukagu similarly asserts that "Generally, critics perceive satire as a literary technique for ridiculing vices in society" (221). It is, therefore, not surprising that many artists across the globe have

continued to use satire for social criticism in their various works. For instance, notable writers like Aristophanes (*Lycistrata*), Moliere (*The Misanthrope*), William Shakespeare (*The Merchant of Venice*), Wole Soyinka (*The Trials of Brother Jero*), and Ngugi Wa Thiong'o (*I Will Marry When I Want*), among many others, have all adeptly deployed satire for social criticism at various times and climes.

Like their counterparts in literature, screenwriters and directors have also adroitly manipulated satire for social criticism as we will soon demonstrate through a critical analysis of Amaka Igwe's "New Pikin 1&2" and "Naija Ninja". Commenting on the nexus between satire and social criticism in literature, Chukwuemeka Ike explains that;

Social criticism is perhaps the most widely acknowledged role of the writer. Every other member of the society seems to look on you, the writer, as the person to speak out against the unpopular government. It is a role that could get you into a maximum-security prison, into forced exile, or even face the firing squad. It could lead to considerable frustration, as you assess what impact if any, your writing has made on the developments around you. On the other hand, it could turn you into a hero. Whichever way things work out; you are likely to have a feeling of relief to know that you have "got it off your chest" by getting out a book or an article in which you have made a point. (223).

Although Ike's view above centers on satire and social criticism in literature, it is nevertheless also valid for screenwriters, for in the final analysis satire irrespective of the mode in which it is used can be fruitfully used for social criticism. By social criticism, we mean the use of art for the condemnation of perceived socio-political and economic abnormalities in society. Social criticism can also be referred to as a "form of academic or journalistic criticism focusing on sociological issues in contemporary society, in particular concerning perceived injustices and power relations in general" (web).

In this study, we are concerned with Horatian satire which, according to M.H. Abrams and Geoffrey Harpham, "uses laughter to criticize human follies and abnormalities" (168), as against Juvenalian satire, which according to them, "uses a dignified and public style of utterance to decry modes of vices and error" and the speaker "undertakes to evoke contempt, moral indignation, or an unillusioned sadness of the observations of men" (168-9). Next comes the theoretical framework for the study. This is necessary to provide the platform for the exegesis of the television dramas being discussed in this paper.

The formalist and sociological theories of art criticism (upon which this study is anchored) constitute some of the most popular theories in contemporary art criticism. In what follows, we will briefly examine their respective tenets to show their appropriateness for this study. To begin with, however, we need to recognize the fact that there is indeed an array of critical perspectives from which any work of art can be gainfully studied. Henry James gives a ballast to this submission in his often quoted assertion that "The house of fiction has not one window, but a million, that there are, in fact, "five million" ways to tell a story, each of it justified if it provides a "center" for the work" (qtd. in Booth 24). As earlier hinted, the present study will be done from a combination of the formalist and sociological theories, and the aim is to demonstrate how Amaka Igwe has successfully deployed satire for social criticism in "New Pikin 1&2" and "Naija Ninja". The choice of the two approaches is based on our conviction that they can enable us successfully to account for the aspects of form and content in these television dramas.

At this juncture, it will be pertinent to briefly review these theories to explain how they will be used in this study. First, the formalist theory. The formalist theory of art emphasizes the

primacy of form and craft of a work of art over its content. B.E.C. Oguzie describes the formalist movement as a "20th-century critical movement which is traced to Aristotle who in his *Poetics* contended that one does not go outside the poem to get the meaning" (11). Wilbur Scott similarly describes formalism as a leading critical movement in recent times. As he puts it: "Without question, it is the most influential critical method of our time" (179). According to M. H. Abrams and Geoffrey Harpham, "formalism is a type of literary theory and analysis which originated in Moscow and St. Petersburg in the second decade of the twentieth century" (138). They further observe that the leading exponents of the formalist movement include Boris Eichenbaum, Victor Shlovsky, and Roman Jakobson, while others like Jan Mukarovsky and Rene Wellek (members of the Prague Linguistic Circle) have greatly contributed to the flowering of the movement in the 1940s (139).

Formalists fervently believe that literature is autochthonous and thus should be judged mainly from literary standards. T. S. Eliot, for instance, asserts that "Although the greatness of literature cannot be determined solely by literary standards... we must remember that whether it is literature or not can be determined only by literary standards" (43). And Wilbur Scott affirms that; There is great literature that has little or no social relevance; social relevance is only one kind of literature and is not central in the theory of literature unless one holds the view that literature is primarily an imitation of life as it is and of social life in particular. But literature is not a substitute for sociology or politics. It has its justification and aim. (109). According to Charles Nnolim, formalist critics are specifically concerned with; The beauty of form, the sheer lyricism of the poetic prose, the delight in the architectonic construction of plots, the charm of ordered patterning, the beauty of total effects through the detailed and subtle analysis of the complex inter-relationships within each work under study. (*Approaches* 10). The technique is, therefore, very significant in formalist criticism of art. Mark Schorer contends that;

Modern criticism has shown that to speak of content as such is not to speak of art at all, but of experience; and that is only when we speak of the achieved content, the form of the work of art, that we speak as critics.... (141).

In socialist criticism, on the other hand, critics turn attention to the relationship between literature and the society in which it is produced. In this regard, Wilbur Scott explains that: Sociological criticism starts with a conviction that art's relations to society are vitally important and that the investigation of these may organize and deepen one's aesthetic response to a work of art. Art is not created in a vacuum; it is the work not simply of a person, but of an author fixed in time and space The sociological critic, therefore, is interested in understanding the social milieu and the extent to which and manner in which the artist responds to it. (123).

It is worth noting that the tenets of the sociological critical movement have been shaped by ideas from Vico, Herder, Taine and Marx and Engels, among many others. Sociological critics strongly believe that beyond its enthralling quality, art has a utilitarian function: to teach, inform, historicize, and correct socio-political anomalies in society. As earlier noted, our choice of the combination of formalist and sociological theories for this study is informed by their capacity to account for both the aspect of technique (satire) and its use for social criticism in Amaka Igwe's television dramas – "New Pikin 1&2" and "Naija Ninja". We strongly agree with scholars like Murray Krieger, Wilbur Scott, and Northrop Frye who opine that a combination of critical approaches can lead to a better illumination of meaning in literary texts. Krieger, for instance, observes that "No theory can adequately account for the diversity of literary experience we would accept as legitimate... nor can it exhaust the meaning and values latent within even the single work (4). Scott similarly asserts that;

It is equally foolish to suppose that any critic deserving of continued attention will stay within the confines of a single approach. On the contrary, he is likely to employ that method – or better those methods in combination- which best suit his knowledge, his particular critical sensibilities, and the work of art before him. (11). And Fyre strongly maintains that;

Criticism must always have two aspects, one turned towards the structure of literature as a whole and one turned towards the other cultural phenomena that form its environment. Together, they balance each other; when one is worked on to the exclusion of the other, the critical perspective goes out of focus. (qtd. in Oguzie 16).

But before going into the discussion of the television dramas, it is pertinent to first present their synopses.

“New Pikin 1 & 2” and “Naija Ninja” belong to the broad category of plays designated as satiric comedy whose quintessential feature is that it provokes laughter that is primarily aimed at unveiling and ridiculing social abnormalities. M. H. Abrams and Geoffrey Harpham define satiric comedy as a form of comedy that “ridicules political policies or philosophical doctrines, or else attacks deviation from the accepted social order by making ridiculous the violators of its standards or morals” (55). In satiric comedy, the writer cleverly pokes fun at the aberrant characters who are often initially ignorant of their moral and social deficiencies and thus arrogantly and ironically perceive others as less knowledgeable and civilized than them. As Stanley Obu has rightly asserted, “the legitimate target of derision” in the comedy “are pomposity, hypocrisy (and) contentiousness”, and “laughter is used... to keep people in line, to ensure conformity to socially accepted norms” (30). As we now gear up to wade into the critical analysis of the television dramas, we ask: so, what, then, are the objects of Amaka Igwe's satiric attack in “New Pikin 1 & 2”? And how did she satirize them in these television dramas?

The first episode: “New Pikin 1&2” exposes Chief Fuji's secret love affair with Caro, which gives them a male child, Taju, who has now grown to a teenage boy. Caro, currently residing in London, brings in her London-based son to meet his estranged father, Chief Fuji, in his office. She introduces Chief Fuji to Taju as his biological father and also teaches him how to greet his father in their Yoruba tradition. Taju feels very happy meeting his father for the first time and looks forward to having a blissful stay with him and his family. Meanwhile, Chief Fuji is confused and wonders how he would accommodate Taju in his house with the ‘battalion’ of children he has already in addition to his three wives - Mama Moji, Peace, and Irete - who are engrossed in endless quarrels. He, therefore, pleads with Caro to take the boy back to London, but Caro refuses and leaves the boy with him.

Left with no other choice, Chief Fuji returns to his house with Taju after closing work and meets his extra-large family at the dining table with their customary commotion (hence the title: *Fuji House of Commotion*). He tells one of his sons, Rabi, to take Taju to the children's room; and also instructs one of his daughters, Jumoke, to give him supper. The family members strive to know the identity of the strange boy, but Chief Fuji tells them that Taju is his friend's son who came on a visit from London. Meanwhile, Taju's arrival and his strange European individualistic lifestyle begin to raise some commotion among Chief Fuji's other children who are strongly rooted in Nigerian traditions and culture. Rabi later takes Taju to their jungle room and gives him a mat to sleep on in any space available in the already over-crowded room. But Taju rejects the mat as well as expresses his dislike for the children's jungle common room. He carries his bag and attempts to leave the house to nowhere in particular. At this point, the other children start laughing at him for what they perceive as his strange behavior and then nickname him “Bow tie”, for he is still wearing a three-piece suit and a bow tie at night which

they deem as utterly ridiculous. They try to persuade him to eat and feel at home, but Taju refuses to eat his food and continues to feel unaccepted.

Meanwhile, Ireti, Chief Fuji's third wife, notorious for her love for exotic foods, prepares what she dubs her usual "sumptuous cookery book meal" and serves it to Chief Fuji to eat, but he frowns at the meal because it is strange to him. Ireti gets upset and complains that Chief Fuji always rejects her "exotic food". However, Chief Fuji makes it known to her that she always cooks unAfrican foods that he is not used to. He, nevertheless, eventually manages to eat the food to please her, and especially to get her co-operation in convincing her co-wives that Taju is one of his friends' sons in London who came for a holiday. Immediately, Peace, Chief Fuji's extraverted second wife, comes into the house and notices the strange boy and asks the children who the strange boy is. They tell her that he is a "new pikin" (new child) and in her usual quarrelsome manner, Peace rushes to Chief Fuji's room to find out who that boy is. Ireti, having been bought over by Chief Fuji, tells Peace that the boy is one of the sons of Chief's friend living in London; that he came for a holiday. Interestingly, Peace is smart enough to decode that the boy is Caro's son. She reveals to her co-wives that Caro was one of Chief Fuji's concubines whom he wanted to marry, but she ran away with a white man to London, and further points out to them that the boy even bears Chief Fuji's native name "Taju", but Chief Fuji denies it. Peace, however, goes further to tell Chief Fuji to share his property among his three wives and their children because she suspects that Chief Fuji's many other children born outside wedlock might still trace their roots back home sooner or later. Taju, on the other hand, goes to Chief Fuji's room to report that the other children were hostile towards him, hence his wish to return to London. Angrily, Chief Fuji summons all the children into his room and flogs them heavily for making Taju's life miserable in "his own father's house", thereby unconsciously admitting that Taju is his biological child. This results in a quarrel between Chief Fuji and his three wives, who consequently demand one form of a settlement or the other because they fear that more of Chief Fuji's children born out of wedlock might still trace their roots back. This marks the end of "New Pikin 1 & 2", and Taju's positive transformation begins in the next episode entitled "Naija Ninja"- a sequel to "New Pikin 1&2".

This episode ("Naija Ninja") shows how Taju, the London – based boy, who finally located his father in Lagos, Nigeria, eventually adapted to his new environment. The drama opens as Peace is happily coming down from Chief Fuji's room, counting the additional feeding money he gave to her in respect of the new person (Taju) added to them. She sees Taju sitting and sleeping at the dining table with an earphone fixed on his ears. Peace perceives this as abnormal and, therefore, interrupts his sleep and orders him to join the other children in their jungle room. Taju reluctantly goes to the children's room; sits uncomfortably at a corner and sleeps, for the entire environment seems to irritate him. The other children, on the other hand, do not like his unsociable attitude towards them, especially Rabi and Gbenro. That is why they pour him water while he is sleeping with his three-piece suit on.

It is now morning, Peace comes to the children's room to wake them up for their morning chores in her usual manner of hitting the tray pan with a stick, but Taju cannot hear her because of the earphone he puts on both ears. Peace taps him and commands him to follow her to the backside of the kitchen, while some other children observe their morning prayers according to the various doctrines of their different religions – Christianity and Islam, representing the two major religious groups in contemporary Nigeria. Taju follows Peace to the backside of the kitchen where she points at a waste bin and asks him to dispose of it at the designated refuse dump within their neighborhood. Grudgingly, Taju carries the waste bin and

carelessly pours it out on the street. Incidentally, two men see him while doing that and command him to pack all of the trash, but Taju refuses, and rather runs back to their house and hides as the two men pursue him back to the house. They fail to find him and then enquire from the two children standing there about the whereabouts of the boy, Taju, which just ran inside the compound, but the little children pretend not to know anything about what the strange men said. These later snowballs into a noisy quarrel between the strange men and the members of Chief Fuji's family.

Ironically, while the other children in Chief Fuji's home courageously face the strange men in the defense of Taju, he cowardly runs into his father's room telling him to call his Mum (Caro) to come and take him back to London, for he is sick and tired of life in Nigeria. He further tells Chief Fuji that he feels very disappointed in him because after spending all his time and energy in search of him, he does not enjoy life. Taju had expected to live a stress - free life on locating his father, Chief Fuji. Chief Fuji, in turn, tells him that he, Taju, is indeed a big disappointment to him (his father) and doubts if his blood flows in him, for if it does, he would not have been there running away from a battle he created, while the rest of the children are out there fighting for him. He then challenges Taju to go out there and prove that he is his true son.

Motivated by that, Taju moves down-stairs, meets the two men, and boldly tells them that he was the one who poured the refuse at the roadside, and not in front of their house, as they claimed. This results in a fierce fight in which Taju beats them up mercilessly, leading to their hasty escape from the compound. Surprised by Taju's heroic exploits, the other children joyfully hail him, while Chief Fuji nods his head with satisfaction. Following that heroic action, Taju turns around and proudly takes Chief Fuji's house as his true home, and the other children as his siblings. He subsequently freely plays, dances, jokes, and sings with them both in traditional African and Westernised styles. Ironically, when a few days later his mother, Caro, comes to take Taju back to London, he surprisingly turns down the offer, for he now feels so much at home in Chief Fuji's house.

Apart from their entertainment value, "New Pikin 1&2" and "Naija Ninja" are also replete with lessons for contemporary Nigerian youths who seem to have imbibed a lot of fake Western cultural values at the detriment of their cultural heritage and sound moral values. The producer, therefore, successfully satirises some of these social aberrations, especially the uncritical inculcation of fake foreign cultural values by African youths in "New Pikin 1 & 2" and "Naija Ninja". It is significant to note that concerned African scholars such as G. Y. Ayaoge and Chidi Maduka have already commented on this sad development. Maduka, for instance, laments that;

The values that shape people's lifestyle in Africa do not derive from African cultural heritage, thereby turning the people into aliens in their various countries. Thus in Nigeria, for example, it is edifying to model the country's constitution on those from Britain and the United States of America, to proudly adopt English and French as the nation's lingua franca without thinking seriously about developing indigenous languages and literature in them, to lionize foreign goods to the detriment of the locally made ones... ("Globalisation and the Criticism" 13). Elsewhere, he similarly, observes that; Nigeria at present prefers foreign goods to locally made ones, hence her inability to effectively tackle the problem of unemployment of the youth, she cherishes the habit of wearing even three-piece suits generally meant for people living in the cold region of the world and not for those in the tropical regions; she generally shies away from the practice of using hands to eat the delicacy of eba/foofoo in hotels for the fear of being considered primitive; and to take one more example, many of their political leaders take pride in investing their loots in Western countries ("Globalisation, Nationhood" 2).

One of such exotic fake values Amaka Igwe condemns in these television plays is the use of improper greeting patterns for elders by contemporary Nigerian children and youths. In these dramas, for instance, we notice that Taju casually greets elders like Chief Fuji and his wives and others in a "hi" style fashionable among Americans and Europeans, and strange to African traditions and culture. While the other children that were home-bred always respectfully greet and prostrate before their elders in traditional Yoruba pattern, Taju merely waves at them and murmurs "hi". On the side of his mother, Caro, we equally notice that she always over – pampers Taju, and unAfricanly calls him "baby", as well as often disapprovingly hugs him as if they were lovers. This is certainly unAfrican and the producer suggests that such an abnormal behavior should not be smuggled into the Nigerian culture. Related to that is Taju's initial inability to adapt to some good aspects of Nigerian culture. For instance, he abnormally wore a suit and a bow-tie to sleep at night and to cap it all, with a set of ear-phone permanently glued to his ears. We also consider his abnormal attitude of constantly clutching computer games and musical gadgets rather absurd and unacceptable. We observed that his addiction to these telecommunication gadgets did not allow him to mix up with other children in the family. Unfortunately, this practice is fast becoming popular among many Nigerian children and youths today. Nkem Adichie has observed in this regard that contemporary African children's addiction to television viewing makes them unable to socialize properly (52).

Furthermore, Taju was also very individualistic and cowardly; easily intimidated by even the smallest members of Chief Fuji's family. The climax of that timidity could be seen when he poured some refuse along the road, leading to his being threatened by two men who chased him into the compound. Rather than stand and defend himself, Taju cowardly ran to the house to complain to Chief Fuji that he was tired of all the challenges he was facing, hence his desire to return to London. However, he underwent a positive metamorphosis when Chief Fuji reprimanded him and encouraged him to learn how to stand up and face challenges courageously. Having been so motivated, Taju came out boldly and successfully fought his aggressors to the amazement of the other children. That incident became a turning point in his life, for henceforth he began to mix up with other children, fight for his rights, sing and dance with others, and indeed, assert his right as an equal member of the family.

The drama ends on a very positive and ironic note, for Taju eventually becomes heroic, accommodating, sociable, competitive, and able to adapt to the positive Nigerian, nay African cultural values. We are, therefore, not surprised when he turns down his mother's request that he should join her and return to London. Nigerian children, especially those bred in the cities and overseas, seriously need to carefully watch this engaging drama and learn from the character transformation of Taju, that fake Western lifestyles (such as individualism) are not ideal for Africans because unlike in Europe and America where individualism is the norm, in Africa, people live together, eat together and confront the challenges of life as a community. The role of Chief Fuji and his wives in training up Taju also deserves commendation. Peace, for instance, constantly corrected Taju each time she noticed that he was going astray. However, it is quite unfortunate to note that this collective approach to training up children seems to be fast disappearing in Nigeria. Some children, therefore, feel free to indulge in negative conduct each time they are not under the immediate control of their parents. In sum, "New Pikin 1 & 2" and "Naija Ninja" are very interesting, didactic, and socially-relevant television dramas through which Amaka Igwe successfully satirised the monster of colonial mentality currently ravaging Nigeria. Amaka Igwe deserves accolades for her artistic dexterity and the social relevance of the

plays in educating African youths on the importance of embracing the positive aspects of their culture rather than uncritically mimicking foreign cultures.

II. Conclusion

New Pikin 1&2” and “Naija Ninja” are very interesting and socially relevant television dramas through which Amaka Igwe captures and condemns the problem of colonial mentality which has resulted in many young Africans uncritically imbibing false western cultural values and jettisoning some good aspects of African culture. Amaka Igwe successfully ridicules this obsessive quest for false western lifestyle among contemporary Africans using Taju who initially exhibited fake western cultural heritage, but eventually ended up a proud African youth.

The researchers strongly commend the producer for her artistic ingenuity and sound moral values she encapsulated in these socially relevant television dramas. They, therefore, recommend the plays with alacrity to parents, teachers, and governments for the entertainment and proper education of contemporary African children and youth.

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